

Analysis of NAAC Accreditation System using ABCD Framework

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ABSTRACT

National Assessment and Accreditation Council (NAAC) is an autonomous institution under University Grants Commission (UGC) of India, established in the year 1994. It has been entrusted with the responsibility of Assessment and Accreditation of Colleges and Universities in India for promotion of quality of teaching-learning and research. Towards this mission, NAAC has been engaged in redesigning its on-going methodologies of Assessment and Accreditation, based on its own field experience, its shared knowledge with other International Quality Assurance Agencies and the quality imperatives in the changing context of world-wide higher education scenario. The mandate of NAAC as reflected in its vision statement is making quality assurance an integral part of the functioning of Higher Education Institutions (HEIs). The accreditation framework of NAAC is based on five core values which include (i) Contributing to National Development, (ii) Fostering Global Competencies among students, (iii) Inculcating a Value System among Students, (iv) Promoting the Use of Technology, (v) Quest for Excellence. These five core values form the foundation for assessment of institutions that volunteer for accreditation by NAAC. The seven criteria identified by NAAC which serve as the basis for assessment of HEIs are (1) Curricular Aspects, (2) Teaching-Learning and Evaluation, (3) Research, Consultancy and Extension, (4) Infrastructure and Learning Resources, (5) Student Support and Progression, (6) Governance, Leadership and Management, and (7) Innovations & Best Practices. In this paper we have analyzed NAAC Accreditation Criteria using our recently developed analyzing framework for business models, operational concepts and functional systems called ABCD technique. The various factors affecting these were found out using focus group method and the constituent critical elements under each factor. The results supported the use of ABCD analyzing technique to a system performance evaluation.

Keywords : ABCD analysis framework, NAAC Accreditation in higher education, HEI, A&A.

I. Introduction

The forces of globalization and liberalization influenced the Indian Higher education in a big way. In a situation where Higher education, similar to the goods and other services has to compete internationally, quality assurance becomes inevitable. Further Indian HEIs operate within a larger framework comprising of several agencies, national contexts and societal expectations and each of these have a unique rendition of the goals. At the functional level, the effectiveness of the HEI is reflected in the extent to which all these layers of goals mutually concur. In such contexts the A&A process is a beginning to bring in uniform quality and position HEIs in such a way that they address more directly the quality provision and the expressed needs of the stakeholders.

National Assessment and Accreditation Council is an autonomous institution of University Grants Commission (UGC) of India, established in the year 1994. Since then it has been entrusted with the responsibility of assessment and accreditation of colleges and universities in India with the mission as to arrange for periodic assessment and accreditation of institutions of higher education or units thereof, or specific academic programmes or projects; to stimulate the academic environment for promotion of quality of teaching-learning and research in higher education institutions; to encourage self-evaluation, accountability, autonomy and innovations in higher education; to undertake quality-related research studies, consultancy and training programmes, and to collaborate with other stakeholders of higher education for quality evaluation, promotion and sustenance. Towards its mission, the NAAC has been engaged, in redesigning its on-going methodologies of Assessment and Accreditation, based on its own field experience, its shared knowledge with other International Quality Assurance Agencies and the quality imperatives in the changing context of world-wide higher education scenario. The mandate of NAAC as reflected in its vision statement is in making quality assurance an integral part of the functioning of Higher Education Institutions (HEIs). The NAAC functions through its General Council (GC) and Executive Committee (EC) where educational administrators, policy makers and senior

academicians from a cross-section of Indian higher education system are represented (NAAC 2013).

The accreditation framework of NAAC is based on five core values detailed below:

(i) **Contributing to National Development** : Contributing to national development has always been an implicit goal of Indian HEIs. The HEIs have a significant role in human resource development and capacity building of individuals, to cater to the needs of the economy, society and the country as a whole, thereby contributing to the development of the nation. Serving the cause of social justice, ensuring equity, and increasing access to higher education are a few ways by which HEIs can contribute to the national development. It is therefore appropriate that the assessment and accreditation (A&A) process of the NAAC looks into the ways HEIs have been responding to and contributing towards this goal.

(ii) **Fostering Global Competencies among Students** : The spiralling developments at the global level also warrant that the NAAC includes in its scope of assessment, skill development of students, on par with their counterparts elsewhere. With liberalization and globalization of economic activities, the need to develop skilled human resources of a high calibre has become imperative. Consequently, the demand for internationally acceptable standards in higher education is evident. Therefore, the accreditation process of NAAC needs to examine the role of HEIs in preparing the students to achieve core competencies, to face the global requirements successfully. This requires that the HEIs be innovative, creative and entrepreneurial in their approach, to ensure skill development amongst the students. Towards achieving this, HEIs may establish collaborations with industries, network with the neighbourhood agencies/bodies and foster a closer relationship between the “world of skilled work” and the “world of competent-learning”.

(iii) **Inculcating a Value System among Students** : Although skill development is crucial to the success of students in the job market, skills are of less value in the absence of appropriate value systems. HEIs have to shoulder the responsibility of inculcating the desirable value systems amongst the students. In a country like India, with cultural pluralities and diversities, it is essential that students imbibe the appropriate values commensurate with social, cultural, economic and environmental realities, at the local, national and universal levels. The seeds of values sown in the early stages of education, mostly aimed at cooperation and mutual understanding, have to be reiterated and re-emphasized at the higher educational institutions through appropriate learning experiences and opportunities. The NAAC assessment therefore

examines how these essential and desirable values are being inculcated in the students, by the HEIs.

(iv) Promoting the Use of Technology : Most of the significant developments that one can observe today can be attributed to the impact of Science and Technology. While the advantages of using modern tools and technological innovations in the day-to-day-life are well recognized, the corresponding changes in the use of new technologies, for teaching – learning and governance of HEIs, leaves much to be desired. Technological advancement and innovations in educational transactions have to be undertaken by all HEIs, to make a visible impact on academic development as well as administration. At a time when our educational institutions are expected to perform as good as their global partners, significant technological innovations have to be adopted. Traditional methods of delivering higher education have become less motivating to the large number of students. To keep pace with the developments in other spheres of human endeavour, HEIs have to enrich the learning experiences of their students by providing them with state- of- the-art educational technologies. The campus community must be adequately prepared to make use of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) optimally. Conscious effort is also needed to invest in hardware, and to orient the faculty suitably. In addition to using technology as learning resources, managing the activities of the institution in a technology-enabled way will ensure effective institutional functioning. For example, documentation and data management in the HEIs are areas where the process of assessment by NAAC has made a significant impact. Moving towards electronic data management and having institutional website to provide ready and relevant information to stakeholders, are desirable steps in this direction. In other words, effective use of ICT in HEIs will be able to provide ICT literacy to the campus community, using ICT for resource sharing and networking, as well as adopting ICT-enabled administrative processes. Therefore, NAAC accreditation would look at how the HEIs have put in place their electronic data management systems and electronic resources and their access to internal and external stakeholders particularly the student community.

(v) Quest for Excellence : Contributing to nation-building and skills development of students, institutions should demonstrate a drive to develop themselves into centres of excellence. Excellence in all that they do, will contribute to the overall development of the system of higher education of the country as a whole. This 'Quest for Excellence' could start with the formation of internal quality assurance cell (IQAC). Another step in this direction could be

the identification of the strengths and weaknesses in the teaching and learning processes as carried out by the institution.

In conformity with the goals and mission of the institution, the HEIs may also add these to their own core values. NAAC assessment lays focus on the institutional developments with reference to three aspects: Quality initiative, Quality sustenance and Quality enhancement. The overall quality assurance framework of NAAC thus focuses on the values and desirable practices of HEIs and incorporates the core elements of quality assurance i.e. internal and external assessment for continuous improvement.

The criteria-based assessment of NAAC forms the backbone of the A&A. The seven criteria represent the core functions and activities of an institution and broadly focus on the issues which have a direct impact on teaching-learning, research, community engagement and the holistic development of the students. The NAAC has identified the following seven criteria to serve as the basis for assessment of HEIs (NAAC 2013) :

1. Curricular Aspects
2. Teaching-Learning and Evaluation
3. Research, Consultancy and Extension
4. Infrastructure and Learning Resources
5. Student Support and Progression
6. Governance, Leadership and Management
7. Innovations and Best Practices

The criteria-based assessment promotes judgment based on values. For example the criterion on “Governance, Leadership and Management” promotes the values such as participation, transparency, team work, systems view, justice, self-reliance and probity in public finance. The Key Aspects identified under each of the seven criteria reflect the processes and values of the HEI on which assessment is made. The questions under each of the Key Aspects focus in particular on the outcomes, the institutional provisions which contribute to these and their impact on student learning and development. The strengths or weaknesses in one area may have an effect on quality in another area. Thus the issues addressed within the Criteria and Key Aspects are closely inter-related and may appear to be overlapping. The criteria and the Key Aspects are not a set of standards or measurement tools by themselves and do not cover everything which happens in every HEI. They are the levers for transformational change and provide an external point of reference for evaluating the quality of the institution under assessment.

ABCD (acronym that stands for Advantages, Benefits, Constraints, and Disadvantages) is an analysis involving examining the efficacy of a business model, operational concept or functional systems bringing the entire gamut of its activity under the preview of six factors namely organizational factors, operational factors, technology, employer-employee issues, customer issues, and social & environmental issues.

II. Literature Review on ABCD Analysis

Recently Aithal et. al. (2015"") developed ABCD analyzing framework to analyze any business model/concept and to study its effectiveness in providing value to its stake holders and sustainable profit through expected revenue generation. Application of ABCD analysis results in an organized list of a business advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages in a systematic matrix. The entire framework is divided under various issues/area of focus and various business deployment factors affecting the business/concept can be identified and analyzed under each issues by identifying suitable critical effective element. This analyzing technique being simple, gives guideline to identify and analyze the effectiveness of any business model and new concepts developed.

Reshma et. al. (2015""), have analysed the characteristics of "Working from Home" e-business model using 'ABCD Analysis Technique'. Based on various factors which decides the Working from Home system, a model of various factors and their constituent critical elements affecting under organizational objectives, employers point of view, employees point of view, customers/students point of view, environmental/societal point of view and system requirements are derived by a qualitative data collection instrument namely focus group method. It is found that the factors supporting advantages and benefits are more effective compare to constraints and disadvantages of this model, so that working from home model may become more popular from the prospective of employers and employees in the organization in the future.

ABCD analysis framework is also used for analysis of Black ocean strategy concept (Aithal et. al. 2015""). The advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages of black ocean strategy on organizational issues, administrative issues, employee's issues, business issues, external environmental issues and operational issues for an organization are identified and analysed by identifying various affecting factors and their constituent critical elements.

III. ABCD Analysis of NAAC Accreditation System

Advantages, Benefits, Constraints and Disadvantages (ABCD) of a System can be used to analyze and understand the model/system in an effective way. As per this analysis technique (Aithal et. al., 2015''a''), the effectiveness of a business model/concept/system can be studied by identifying and analyzing the advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages by considering various issues like Organizational Issues, Faculty Performance Issues, Students support- progression Issues, Social/Environmental/Community engagement issues, Issues on Infrastructure, Learning resources & Research, and Governance, leadership and Innovations issues as in the block diagram of issues affecting the NAAC Accreditation System and is shown in fig. 1. The various factors contributing under the four identified constructs like advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages are derived by a qualitative data collection instrument namely focus group method (Rogers and Hunt, 1994, Morgan and Hunt, 1994) and the constituent critical elements supporting these factors are identified. Table 1 shows the framework of ABCD model in terms of advantages, benefits, constraints and disadvantages in terms of determinant issues mentioned above and the key issues coming under them [Aithal et. al. (2015''a'')].

Fig. 1 : Block diagram of issues affecting the NAAC Accreditation system as per ABCD framework.

Table 1 : Analysis of NAAC accreditation system using ABCD framework.

Key Issues	Advantages	Benefits	Constraints	Disadvantages
I. ORGANISATIONAL ISSUES				

1. Organizational Structure	Defined organization structure	Greater decentralization	Reduced accountability	Formal structure/hierarchy
2. Administrative Issues	Systematic functioning	Standard policies and procedures	Time consuming administrative system	Rigid practices
3. Enrollment	Diversified admission strategy	Student diversity	Merit diluted	Influx of low profile students
4. Strategic Planning	Autonomy in design and development	Easy to impart	Weak stakeholder readiness	Low opportunity for maneuverability
5. Corporate and Business Strategy	Promoting growth strategy	Emphasis on research orientation and learning culture	Vast focus	Limited resources and recognition
6. Alumni as an Asset	Increasing alumni base	Round the year activity with alumni connections	Retaining interest of alumni	Time as a scarce resource for alumni
7. Placement	Placement support	Value addition to the course	Less opportunity	Limited capability
II. FACULTY PERFORMANCE ISSUES				
1. Teaching-Learning	Action plan and teaching aids	Enhanced learning practices	Teacher- learner incompatibility	Continuous improvement
2. Faculty Diversity	Versatile faculty	Better adaptability	Student- teacher gap	Limited exposure
3. Staff Development Programmes	Improved efficiency	Personal & career growth	Scarcity of opportunity	Retaining interest
4. Faculty Support Systems	Better outcome	Motivated and committed	Inadequate resources	Positive mindset
5. Faculty Assessment	Performance management system	Regular and continuous	Subjectivity	Refining criteria of efficiency
6. Faculty Empowerment	Simplifying task	Collective learning	Choice of approach	Inability to combat multiple task
III. STUDENT SUPPORT - PROGRESSION ISSUES				
1. Information Dissemination	Diverse methods	Ensures coverage in all modes	Vigil round the year	Repetition and monotony
2. Inclusive efforts	Social commitment	Expanding opportunity	Financial constraints	Institutional competition with agencies
3. Student Development	More entrepreneurs	Unemployment reduced	Low preference	Success not assured
4. Student Satisfaction	Effective grievance and counseling mechanism	Effective service	Diluted student initiative	Grievances persisting
5. Exposure	More industrial visits and guest	Interesting learning	Resource crunch	Time management

	lectures	opportunity		
6. Student Participation	Enriched campus life	All-round development	Diminishing student interest	Optimum priority
7. Leadership Development	Participation in activities	Develop competitive spirit	Balancing interest	Some are left out
IV. SOCIAL/ENVIRONMENTAL/COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT ISSUES				
1. Social Concern	Service orientation	Building institution-community network	Resource constraints	Unrealistic expectation
2. Outreach activities	Civic responsibility	Students exposed to national reconstruction	Low priority	Limited reach
3. Student Involvement	Exposure	Understanding Social/community issues	Limits to involving	Diverting form academics
4. Environmental Concerns	Addressing cross cutting issues	Fulfilling existential priorities	Magnitude of the problem	Tiny and piece meal efforts
V. ISSUES ON INFRASTRUCTURE, LEARNING RESOURCES & RESEARCH				
1. Facilities	Favourable to academic ambience	Congenial atmosphere for learning	Maintenance of facilities with time	Diluted focus on academics
2. Learning Resource	Effective and user friendly	Better augmentation	Time constraints	Not adequate utilization
3. Technology Deployment	Plethora of educational aides	Supplement classroom learning	Unlimited opportunity	Limited availability
4. Research Promotion	Pro-research orientation	Develops scientific temper	Induced gradually	Insufficiently qualified faculty
5. Collaboration	Sharing and pooling	Superiority through synergy	Reduced responsibility	One sided involvement
VI. GOVERNANCE, LEADERSHIP & INNOVATIONS ISSUES				
1. Realizing vision & mission	Focused effort	Contribute to nation building	Concerted effort required	Limited reach
2. Adherence to quality	Improved performance	Good products	Continuous pursuit	Challenges to working in teams
3. Academic leadership	Empowered faculty	Role performance	Motivation	Sustaining interest reduced
4. Decentralization	Shared responsibility	Contribute more	Accountability reduced	Authority diluted
5. Strategy development & deployment	Perspective plan	Multiple focus	Involving stakeholders	Articulating strategies
6. Student feedback	Detecting flaws	Make up for defects	Impractical demands	One sided impression
7. Faculty retention	Rewarding potentials	Maintaining efficiency	Building long term goals	Possibility of errors
8. Innovations	New experiments	Better examples	Limited initiative	Un-assured success

The various key issues identified under the determinant organizational issues are : Organizational structure; Administrative issues; Student enrollment; Strategic planning; Corporate and business strategy; Alumni as an asset; and Placement. The various key issues identified under the determinant faculty performance issues are : Teaching-Learning; Faculty diversity; Staff development programmes; Faculty support systems; Faculty assessment; Faculty empowerment. The various key issues identified under the determinant student support & progression issues are : Information dissemination; Inclusive efforts; Student development; Student satisfaction; Exposure; Student participation; and Leadership development. The various key issues identified under the determinant social/environmental/community engagement issues are : Social concern; Outreach activities; Student involvement; and Environmental concerns. The various key issues identified under the determinant issues on infrastructure, learning resources, and research are : Facilities; Learning resource; Technology deployment; Research promotion; and Collaboration. The various key issues identified under the determinant issues governance, leadership and innovations are : Realizing vision & mission; Adherence to quality; Academic leadership; Decentralization; Strategy development & deployment; Student feedback; Faculty retention; and Innovations. The advantages, benefits, constraints and disadvantages of the above key issues under each determinant issue are listed in table 1.

IV. Critical Constituent Elements as per ABCD model

As per ABCD framework [Aithal et. al. (2015”c”) and Reshma et.al. (2015”b”)] for **NAAC Accreditation System** affecting under Organizational Issues, Faculty Performance Issues, Students development Issues, Social/Environmental/Community engagement issues, issues on Infrastructure and learning resources, Issues on Innovations, Creativity and Best Practices are identified. The critical constituent elements of these factors are listed under the four constructs - advantages, benefits, constraints and disadvantages of the ABCD technique and tabulated in tables 2 to 5.

Table 2 : Advantages of NAAC accreditation system.

Particulars	Factors affecting	Constituent Elements	Critical
Organizational Issues	Defined organization Structure	Organizational structure	
	Systematic functioning	Administrative Issues	
	Diversified admission strategy	Enrollment	
	Autonomy in design and	Strategic planning	

	development	
	Promoting growth strategy	Corporate and Business strategy
	Increasing alumni base	Alumni as an asset
	Placement support	Placement
Faculty Performance Issues	Action plan and teaching aids	Teaching -learning
	Versatile Faculty	Faculty diversity
	Improved efficiency	Staff development programs
	Better outcome	Faculty support system
	Performance management system	Faculty assessment
	Simplifying Task	Faculty empowerment
Student support-progression Issues	Student diversity	Student intake
	Resourcefulness	Student development
	High standards	Student assessment
	Placement opportunities	Industry readiness
Social/Environmental/Community engagement issues	Opportunity to all	Education opportunity
	High	Education standards
	Encourages community activities	Social commitment
	More job opportunities within country and outside	Educated /Skilled workforce
Issues on Infrastructure, Learning resources and Research	Basic Facilities	Physical facilities
	Enhances knowledge, Learning and sharing	Library facilities
	ICT for a range of activities	IT infrastructure
	To help physically challenged and special students	Special requirements
Governance, Leadership & Innovations Issues	High	Research and development
	Encouraged	Consultancy
	High involvement	Technology and related aids
	Regular basis	Industry interaction

Table 3 : Benefits of NAAC accreditation system.

Particulars	Factors affecting	Critical Constituent Elements
Organizational Issues	Greater de-centralization	Organizational hierarchy
	Standard policies and procedures	Administration
	Student diversity	Student Enrollment
	Easy to impart	Program curriculum
	Emphasis on research orientation and learning culture	Organizational culture
	Round the year activity with alumni connections	Alumni support
	Value addition to the course	Industry connections
Faculty Performance Issues	Enhanced learning practices	Teaching learning practices
	Better adaptability	Teacher quality

	Personal and career growth	Career development
	Motivated and committed	Faculty support
	Regular and continuous	Faculty assessment
	Collective Learning	Empowerment
Students development Issues	Competitive spirit	Student diversity
	Student centric	Student activities
	Transparency	Assessment
	Independent thinkers	Values /ethics/corporate social citizenship
Social/Environmental/Community engagement issues	High quality education standards	World class standards
	Skill/knowledge improvement	Human development
	More job opportunities	Industry development
	Involve in community activities	Social responsibility
Infrastructure And Learning resources	Modest	Design and Layout
	Latest books and technology	Library facility
	Both hard ware and software development. Adequate training	Technology up gradation
	Investment	Building and machinery
Issues on Innovations Creativity and Best Practices	Risk taking behavior encouraged	Culture
	Democratic	Leadership style
	Diverse people in a team	Team work
	Quality conscious and continuous improvement	Quality [IQAC]

Table 4 : Constraints of NAAC accreditation System.

Particulars	Factors affecting	Critical Constituent Elements
Organizational Issues	Reduced accountability	Institutional apathy
	Time consuming administrative system	Lengthy procedures
	Merit diluted	Compromising to situations
	Weak stakeholder readiness	Low concern
	Vast Focus	Too many issues
	Retaining interest of alumni	Perception of role
	Less opportunity	Factors beyond control
Faculty Performance Issues	Teacher-learner incompatibility	Student expectations
	Student –Teacher gap	Built-in distance
	Scarcity of opportunity	Frequency of activities
	Inadequate resources	Limited focus
	Subjectivity	Closed mind
	Choice of approach	Misunderstanding of individual requirement
Students support & progression Issues	Vigil round the year	Tardiness
	Financial constraints	Unproductive
	Low preference	Risk feeling
	Diluted student initiative	Low awareness

	Resource crunch	Low priority
	Diminishing student interest	Addressing student concerns
	Balancing interest	Rejuvenating interest
Social/Environmental/Community Engagement Issues	Resource constraints	Fund mobilization
	Low priority	Re-structuring curriculum
	Involving	Personal and familial reasons
	Magnitude of the problem	Too many contributors
Issues on Infrastructure, Learning resources and Research	Maintenance of facilities on time	Delay & neglect
	Time constraints	Lethargy
	Unlimited opportunity	Identification of appropriateness
	Induced gradually	Consistent efforts
Governance, Leadership & Innovations Issues	Reduced responsibility	Individual contribution
	Concerted effort required	Gaining support
	Continuous pursuit	Hard work
	Motivation	Poor motivators
	Accountability reduced	Fear of blame
	Involving stakeholders	Reduced interest
	Impractical demands	Unlimited expectations
	Building long term goals	Career plans
	Limited initiative	Low pro-active orientation

Table 5 : Disadvantages of NAAC accreditation system.

Particulars	Factors affecting	Critical Constituent Elements
Organizational Issues	Formal structure /Hierarchy	Misconception
	Rigid Practices	Customary behavior
	Influx of low profile students	Poor screening
	Low opportunity for maneuverability	Lack of institutional readiness
	Limited resources and recognition	Vast potential of human resources
	Time as a scarce resource for alumni	Adopting innovative ways
	Limited capability	Enlarging collaborations
Faculty Performance Issues	Continuous improvement	Faculty development programmes
	Limited exposure	In-house training
	Retaining interest	Increasing relevance
	Positive mindset	Enhancing experiences
	Refining criteria of efficiency	Continuous improvement
	Inability to combat multiple Task	Loading with pace
Students support & progression Issues	Repetition and monotony	Increase attractions
	Institutional competition with agencies	Setting example
	Success not assured	Learning from failure
	Grievances persisting	Increased faith

	Time management	Better co-ordination
	Optimum priority	Developing talent
	Some are left out	Encouraging the weak
Social/Environmental/Community Engagement Issues	Unrealistic expectation	Community feedback
	Limited reach	Accepting slow progress
	Diverting form academics	Recognition of goal
	Tiny and piece meal efforts	Worthy of fulfillment
Issues on Infrastructure, Learning Resources & Research	Diluted focus on academics	Facilities as prerequisites
	Not adequate utilization	Promote utilization
	Limited availability	Develop new tools
	Insufficiently qualified faculty	Upgradation
	One sided involvement	Common goals
Governance, Leadership and Innovations Issues	Limited reach	Contribution worthwhile
	Challenges to working in teams	Trust & mutual respect
	Sustaining interest reduced	Sharing & improving
	Authority diluted	Bottom-up approach
	Articulating strategies	Better reasoning
	One sided impression	Corroborated for facts
	Possibility of errors	Management by result
	Un-assured success	Trial & error approach

V. Conclusion

We have studied the features of NAAC accreditation system based on ABCD analysis framework. Various factors affecting the issues of the system along with their constituent critical elements are identified and analyzed. It is found that the factors supporting advantages and benefits are more effective compare to constraints and disadvantages of this system, so that NAAC accreditation system may become more popular from the prospective of the administration and academic progress in the organization in the future. The system supports the student's progress with appropriate intervention based upon a detailed knowledge of individuals. NAAC include and lead to the complete progress and personal development of each individual. The system is able to cultivate a partnership particularly with parents, industries and the community as a whole to support a students learning and progress. The results supported the use of ABCD analyzing technique to a system performance evaluation.

An analysis of NAAC accreditation system based on ABCD analyzing framework has brought out dominant *determinant issues* and inherent *kay issues*. The discussion of benefits accrued from the advantages of addressing the key issues fulfills quality concerns in any institution. The critical constituent elements are critical or decisive in the success of addressing the key issues through the inputs demanded in the advantages. While mechanisms have to be put in place to address the key issues to enhance quality, it has to take care of the

constraints and disadvantages in a positive way. In other words, constraints and disadvantages signals the success of the inputs through critical constituent elements being prime variable of change. NAAC accreditation system may become popular from the perspective of educational administration and academic governance in higher educational institutions in the future. The framework suggested by NAAC is based on appropriate intervention in the key areas brought forward in the analyzing framework. The system is a co-partnership between teachers, students, institutions, parents, industries (employer) and the community as a whole to support student's learning and progress to fulfill the purpose of education for personal gain and national goals.

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